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In situ non-invasive characterization of the composition of Pompeian pigments preserved in their original bowls

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ABSTRACT

Pigments are one of the most important archaeological records recovered from the burial of Pompeii. Therefore, their analysis and characterization is an important task from the historical, archaeological and chemical point of view. In this work, a unique collection of various coloured raw pigments conserved in their original bowls recovered from the archaeological excavations of Pompeii was characterized. Nowadays, these pigments are stored both in the Naples National Archaeological Museum (MANN) and in the Applied Research

Laboratory from the archaeological site of Pompeii (ARLP) due to its high archaeological value. For the molecular analysis, in situ micro-Raman spectroscopy was used and the elemental characterization was conducted by means of hand-held energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence (HH-ED-XRF). Mercury sulfide (HgS) and red ochre (hematite, Fe_2O_3) were identified in different red pigments and yellow ochre (goethite, FeOOH) in the analyzed yellow colours. The analyzed blue pigments were Pompeian blue ($\text{CaCuSi}_4\text{O}_{10}$) in all cases, green pigments were composed mainly by malachite ($\text{Cu}_2\text{CO}_3(\text{OH})_2$) and the white one resulted to be dolomite. Pink powders appeared to be lake pigments, using madder lake (alizarin and purpurin) as organic colorant in order to dye the inorganic mordant (local clays). In the case of blue and pink pigments Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed in order to see similarities/differences in the elemental composition among samples of the same colour. Groups within samples of the same colour were identified pointing out different sources of the raw material or enrichments in leachable metals present in soils during the burial.

Keywords: Archaeological pigments from Pompeii, micro-Raman spectroscopy, hand-held X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy, Principal Component Analysis, non-invasive analysis, in situ analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Pompeii is one of the most important and famous archaeological cities of the world due to the event occurred in year 79 AD when Vesuvius volcano erupted [1]. This catastrophe killed thousands of habitants [2] and buried completely this city of the Ancient Rome. However, this event also brought with it benefits that people can enjoy nowadays, such as having a walk through streets that date back from BC period. Moreover, many original paintings can be seen in the archaeological city. Unfortunately, they are suffering different deterioration processes due to the exposure to the present polluted atmosphere [3-4]. For this reason, some of the wall paintings are conserved in the Naples National Archaeological Museum (MANN) for their optimal preservation [5].

Red, yellow, green and blue were the most used colours to decorate the houses [6]. This colour palette covers a large percentage of the visible colours of the wall paintings. The pigments related to them were usually obtained from three different sources. The easiest and cheapest way was taking coloured earths [7]. In this sense, red and yellow ochres, iron-rich soils with reddish to yellow hues, can be mentioned [8]. Another way of obtaining pigments was crushing coloured minerals such as malachite ($\text{Cu}_2\text{CO}_3(\text{OH})_2$, green) or cinnabar (HgS from natural origin, red) [9]. The last way of obtaining pigments was through a chemical reaction, like the preparation of Pompeian blue ($\text{CaCuSi}_4\text{O}_{10}$, blue), or through a more sophisticated mixture of organic and inorganic compounds, which lead to the so-called lake pigments. A lake pigment is formed by the precipitation of an organic colorant upon an insoluble inorganic substrate, usually called mordant, which forms the matrix of the pigment.

The organic colorant was usually obtained from plants or molluscs and the extracted dye was mixed with clays [10].

The study and characterization of pigments is a very interesting task for increasing the knowledge about a particular culture or civilization [11]. Moreover, pigments have a particular chronology. It is well known that ochres and green earths have been used since the prehistory [12, 13], malachite and cinnabar since the Egyptian empire period, as well as the Egyptian blue (similar to the Pompeian blue pigment), and Tyrian purple since Ancient Rome [14]. Thus, the identification of a particular pigment can contextualize that civilization or artwork in a certain period of the history. In this sense, during the last years many works have showed the characterization of the pigments of some Pompeian wall paintings with the aim of identifying the used materials [4-6], and thereby obtaining useful information about social and historical aspects (e.g. source of the material, manufacturing ways,...).

Apart from that, from the chemical point of view, to know the original composition of the pigments can lead to identify degradations that happen due to processes caused by natural or anthropogenic sources [15-18]. It must be remarked that the pigments present in the wall paintings have been exposed for decades to the actual polluted atmosphere, they have been restored, some waxes have been applied over them, etc., making difficult an exhaustive characterization of the original composition. Fortunately, in the case of Pompeii, during the excavations that started in the XVIII century, many original pigment powders conserved in their original pottery bowls have been recovered from the burial. Therefore, thanks to these

unique archaeological records, the original ancient composition of the pigments can be obtained. In this sense, many are the works dealing with the characterization of recovered Pompeian pigments [19, 22]. Apart from the simple characterization, the statistical study of the obtained elemental information between samples of the same color is a very interesting tool in order to identify differences that could give additional information regarding their possible different origin or provenance. To the author knowledge, there are no works in the literature dealing with the statistical analysis of the elemental information extracted from the analysis of Pompeian pigments. Thus, this study could provide a useful tool or strategy in the initial step of predicting different provenances of original raw pigments recovered from the burial site of ancient Pompeii.

Due to the singularity and the low quantity available, scientific researches of archaeological records (and by extension all those belonging to the entire Built Cultural Heritage) are often very limited due to sampling restrictions. Thus, the use of portable/hand-held (HH) non-invasive techniques to conduct this type of analysis in the archaeological and cultural heritage field is usually mandatory [23-31] and always very appealing.

For that reason, the use of non-invasive techniques is the best option for the analysis of pigments because samples are not affected, and therefore, these archaeological records can be maintained in their original state. In this sense, the use of molecular techniques is fundamental for this research in order to identify the molecular composition of the pigments. One of the most used techniques for the molecular characterization of this type of samples

is Raman spectroscopy [32-33]. The non-invasive character of the measurements together with the technological development that portable spectrometers have suffered in the last years (leading in high quality spectra with very good signal-to-noise ratio) have converted Raman spectroscopy into the main technique used in cultural heritage analysis. Whenever it is possible, molecular techniques are usually assisted or combined with elemental measurements to obtain a complete characterization. Elemental analysis is usually performed by means of energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (ED-XRF) [34-36] thanks to its non-invasive feature. The success of these techniques also lies on the fact that they are fast and cheap. Thus, the best strategy would be the direct application of portable/HH instrumentation in situ (in the museum or in a storage room, for example) to obtain reliable results [4,16].

In this work, a unique collection of various coloured raw pigments conserved in their original pottery bowls/shell recovered from the archaeological excavations of Pompeii was characterized in situ (in the store room of the museum or in the ARLP itself), so that the necessity of taking samples to study in the laboratory was avoided. Nowadays, they are stored and preserved both in the Naples National Archaeological Museum (MANN) and in the Applied Research Laboratory from the archaeological site of Pompeii (APRL) due to its high archaeological value. Therefore, a non destructive characterization of the pigments under study is mandatory. To the author knowledge, there are not works dealing with an in situ non destructive characterization of Pompeian raw pigments. Thus, in this work a non destructive

in situ method based on the molecular analysis performed by a portable Raman spectrometer coupled to a portable video-microscope and elemental characterization conducted by means of a HH-ED-XRF spectrometer was used. Apart from the simple elemental and molecular characterization, for those colours with high number of available samples, chemometric analysis was also performed by means of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) using the obtained multivariate elemental data. Thanks to this statistical study, similarities and/or differences among different samples of the same colours were identified and an explanation for these results was proposed (e.g. different provenances of the raw material or different locations in the burial).

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Samples

As mentioned before, pigments of different colours (see Table 1) with high archaeological value conserved in their original pottery bowls/shell were considered in this work (see Fig. 1). The analysis was carried out in situ in the MANN storeroom or in the ARLP.

Table 1. Samples under study (reference number underlined for those samples belonging to MANN).

COLOR	NUMBER OF SAMPLES	REFERENCE NUMBERS
Blue	7	1806, 9535, 9649, 12011, 48562, <u>117333</u> , <u>117338</u>
Pink	6	18103, 18107, <u>117323</u> , <u>117342</u> , 117345, <u>117365</u>
Green	2	<u>11699</u> , 41505

Red	2	64628, <u>112251</u>
Yellow	2	<u>117274</u> , <u>117359</u>
White	1	<u>117368</u>

Fig. 1. Some of the studied pigments (in the left part) in their original bowls and in a shell: a) 117333 blue b) 11699 green c) 117366 yellow and d) 64628 red; In the right part, measuring the pigments directly by Raman spectroscopy in the ARLP.

Most of the pigments were conserved in their original bowls (see Fig. 1A, Fig. 1B and Fig. 1C). However, as shown in Fig 1D, red pigment 64628 was conserved in a shell. According to the person in charge of the ARLP, the shell was the container for the pigments powders used by the artists when they were painting the frescoes. Thus, it is supposed that this particular pigment was ready or being used in the moment of the eruption in year 79 AD. For that reason, this is a special Pompeian pigment sample, very interesting to be analyzed. On

the other hand, some works can be found in the literature dealing with red and purple powders contained in shells [37-41] with painting or cosmetic purposes..

2.2 In Situ Analytical Methodology

For the micro-Raman measurements, some grains of each raw pigment were taken from each bowl and were deposited on a previously cleaned microscope slide for their direct measurement. After the measurements the pigment grains were returned to their original bowl in order to prevent from loss of sample. For the analysis two portable Raman spectrometers were used. On the one hand, a portable innoRam™ Raman spectrometer (B&WTEK_{INC.}, Newark, USA) provided with a CleanLaze® technology 785 nm excitation laser (< 300 mW laser output power) was used. The instrument implements a controller of the laser power (a scale from 0 to 100% of the total power of the laser). To prevent pigments thermal decomposition, laser power was carefully controlled. It also includes a two dimensional charge coupled device (CCD) to detect the dispersed Raman signal, which is Thermo-electric Cooled (TC) to -20 °C to maximize the dynamic range by reducing dark current. A back-thinned CCD is used to obtain 90% quantum efficiency via collection of incoming photons at wavelengths that would not pass through a front illuminated CCD. A spectral resolution of 4.0 cm⁻¹ (measured at 912 nm) can be achieved with a double pass transmission optic. The spectra were acquired between 65-3000 cm⁻¹.

On the other hand, a portable innoRam™ BWS445-532S (B&W TEK_{INC.}, Newark, USA) spectrometer was also used. In this case, the wavelength of the excitation laser implemented is

of 532 nm (45 mW laser output power) and the Raman signals were also collected by a CCD detector refrigerated by Peltier effect. The spectral range of the Raman instrument is 65-3750 cm^{-1} with an average spectral resolution of 5 cm^{-1} (measured at 609 nm). With both spectrometers, the spectra were acquired for 1-15 seconds and 5-30 accumulations in order to improve the signal-to-noise ratio. The spectral acquisition and data treatment was performed using the BWSpecTM v.4.0215 (B&WTEK_{INC.}, Newark, USA) and OMNIC 7.2 (Thermo, Massachusetts, USA) softwares for both cases. Both Raman spectrometers were coupled to a BAC151B portable video-microscope (BWtek, USA), which has a TV micro-camera that allows focusing the different grains of the matrix. For the microscopic study a 20x (8.8 mm working distance and 105 μm laser beam spot size) and 50x (3.68 mm working distance and 42 μm laser beam spot size) objective lens were used. Moreover, the positioning of the portable video-microscope is controlled by a micrometric stage and thanks to the dual laser wavelength optic port system it can be coupled to both spectrometers which implement both laser wavelengths. The obtained Raman spectra were treated using Omnic V.7.2 (Nicolet) software. The interpretation of all the Raman results was performed by comparing the acquired Raman spectra with Raman spectra of pure standard compounds collected in the e-VISNICH dispersive Raman database [42]. Additionally, free Raman databases (e.g. RRUFF [43]) were also considered for the assignation of Raman bands.

For the in situ elemental characterization of the pigments, an XMET5100 (Oxford Instruments, UK) HH-ED-XRF spectrometer was used. For the measurement of the pigments, the device was fixed in a stand. A few amount of each pigment was taken from the bowl with a previously cleaned spatula and it was placed in the sampling interface covering the whole

measuring area. Before depositing the pigment grains, a SpectroMembrane® Mylar thin-film sample support window of 2.5 μm thick (Chemplex Industries, Inc., Palm City, USA) was placed over the sampling interface and the raw pigment was deposited on it. . After the analysis of each pigment, the used amount of sample was returned to its corresponding bowl. The HH-ED-XRF instrument is equipped with an Rh X-ray tube working at a maximum voltage of 45 kV. The size of the emitted X-ray beam is 9 mm. The analyzer includes a silicon drift detector (SDD) of high resolution that is able to provide an energy resolution of 150 eV (FWHM of the Mn $K\alpha$ line). Besides, the analyzer contains a PDA to control the spectrometer and save the spectral and quantitative information. In order to determine possible contributions from the setup of the instrument, such as the detector and possible contaminations coming from the XRF analyzer window, 20 repetitive spectra of an instrumental blank (a PTFE block) were acquired before each measurement batch. To improve the limit of detection, the spectra were acquired during 100 s (real time) and the voltage and current of the X-ray tube was set at 45 kV and 15 μA respectively. In order to improve the detection of the light elements ($Z < 25$), lower voltage (13 kV) and higher current (45 μA) was used. Although the software is based on the use of Fundamental Parameters quantification methods, in this work, the net areas of $K\alpha$ lines of each detected element in the spectrum were considered, performing a previous normalization process. Further details are given elsewhere [44].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Red pigments

Two red samples were analyzed, on the one hand a brownish red pigment conserved in an original bowl (sample 112251), and on the other hand, a brilliant red powder conserved in a shell (sample 64628, see Fig. 1D). The Raman spectrum acquired in situ in the ARLP, using the 532 nm laser for the red pigment sample with reference number 64628, is shown in Fig. 2. The observed bands at 253, 284 and 343 cm^{-1} correspond to those of mercury sulphide (HgS). In this case, it belongs to a cinnabar mineral, since in the Roman period the mercury sulphide red pigment was obtained from natural sources [45] and the synthetic route was discovered hundreds of years later. Therefore, the presence of cinnabar as the main compound responsible of giving its characteristic brilliant reddish colour was confirmed. Apart from the molecular characterization, elemental analysis was also performed by means of HH-ED-XRF to complement and confirm the obtained molecular results. The acquired XRF spectrum for this red pigment confirmed the previous Raman results, since the major elements present in the sample were S and Hg (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Red pigment 64628. Raman and HH-ED-XRF in situ acquired spectra.

The use of cinnabar at that time was an indicator of richness because it was scarce and difficult to process, increasing in this way the price of this brilliant red pigment. Consequently, cinnabar has been identified in Pompeian luxurious houses, whose owners belonged to the high class of that period [45].

Red ochre, in contrast, was a cheaper red pigment, used usual and constantly because it was obtained from iron-rich soils. The in situ Raman spectrum (acquired in the storeroom of MANN) of the red pigment 112251 is shown in Fig. 3, in which the typical bands of hematite (α -Fe₂O₃) at 224, 243, 291, 404 and 608 cm⁻¹ can be observed. In this case, the 785 nm excitation laser was used to avoid fluorescence effect that usually 532 nm laser promotes in ochre samples due to the clays or alumino-silicates presence in this type of pigments. Apart from the identified hematite, quartz (α -SiO₂) was also found as minor compound in sample 112251 by means of portable Raman spectroscopy.

Fig. 3. Raman spectra of red pigment 112251.

This red ochre pigment was also analyzed by HH-ED-XRF to determine its elemental composition. The major element present in the pigment was Fe, together with Al, Si, K, Ti, V, Cu, Zn, Sr and Zr (see Fig. S1), confirming in this way that it is a red ochre because: a) the elements Al, Si and K are probably due to the presence of the feldspars (potassium aluminosilicates) present in the raw soil used to obtain the ochre pigment, and b) other elements are also coming from the used soil since they are characteristic from the Somma-Vesuvius and surrounding area, especially Sr and Zr, which are typical volcanic elements [46].

3.2 Green pigments

For the molecular characterization of green samples (labelled 11699 and 41505), the 532 nm excitation laser was selected since better Raman results are systematically obtained using this excitation wavelength for green colour pigments. For both green samples, malachite (characteristic bands at 155, 179, 221, 269, 352, 433, 534, 719, 1088, 1367 and 1494 cm^{-1} , see Fig. 4) was identified. This green mineral ($\text{Cu}_2\text{CO}_3(\text{OH})_2$) was usually crushed in order to obtain a fine powder to be used as pigment [47].

Fig. 4. Raman spectrum of green pigment samples 41505 (red) and 11699 (blue).

Apart from this green mineral, quartz was also identified by means of Raman spectroscopy, as in the case of red ochre pigment. To complement molecular results, both green samples were also analyzed by means of HH-ED-XRF, obtaining spectra in which Cu was the major element, together with Ca and Si (see Fig. S2), which probably come from various silicates that accompany the bulk pigment. Apart from these elements, a high presence of Pb should be remarked. Considering that these pigments were buried for hundreds of years, possible enrichments of leachable metals could be occurred. These metals are present in the volcanic material transformed into the current soils by natural weathering processes. In this sense, a previous work [10] demonstrated the enrichment of Pb in Pompeian buried pigments. Thus, in this case, the presence of Pb in these green pigments could be caused by this leaching process.

3.3 Pink pigments

The Raman spectra using the 532 nm excitation laser obtained from pink samples did not give useful information for the identification of the compound responsible of the colour. In a previous work [10], the inorganic binder of three of this set of six pink samples were deeply characterized, obtaining, by means of X-Ray diffraction (XRD), that they were mainly composed by an amorphous to poorly crystalline aluminosilicate clay. These type of clays used as inorganic matrixes were mixed with an organic colorant to obtain a pink lake pigment as result. The used clays give high fluorescence when excited with the 532 nm laser, masking any Raman band. Thus, a pretreatment of the sample is usually done, the organic colorants are extracted and the final extracts are measured by Surface Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS), which provides much better results than the usual direct Raman measurements [48]. In these pigments, madder lake (mainly alizarin and purpurin anthraquinonic dyes) was identified as the main organic colorant responsible of the pinkish colour.

Apart from the identification of the organic colorant, since the number of pink samples was high, a complete in situ elemental characterization by XRF was performed in order to study possible similarities and differences on the elemental composition of the matrix. For that, the net counts of the detected elements normalized against Compton line of each measurement were used to perform the chemometric analysis. In this sense, an initial study was performed in order to obtain a preliminary overview about the variability and correlation of the elemental composition of pink samples (see Fig. S3 and S4 respectively). Thanks to this previous chemometric analysis, it was observed that most of the elements present in pink samples were highly correlated (see Fig. S4), although others, such as Al, Cu, Ca, Si and Fe were not correlated and showed high variability (see Fig. 4). Once this previous analysis was

done, the Principal Component Analysis was performed. The data set for the pink samples consisted of a matrix with 18 analyses in rows and the normalized net counts of 9 elements (P, Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Ni, Cu, Zn and Sr) in columns (variables). The PCA model with two principal components, explaining the 76% of the variance, was chosen as the most reliable/accurate one (see Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Principal Component Analysis of the analyzed pink samples (bi-plot representation).

In the plot shown in Fig. 5 a clear difference can be observed among the analyzed samples. In particular, PC2 divides the samples belonging to the deposit of ARLP (positive values) from those belonging to MANN (negative values). Samples from ARLP are richer in Al, Ni, Cr and Zn. However, samples from MANN show higher levels in P and Cu. These differences between samples from different deposits (ARLP vs MANN) could be related to different

provenances and/or procedures of manufacturing the lake pigments. More concretely, clays taken from different places could have been used to produce the final pigment, leading to different elemental compositions of the inorganic part of the lake pigment. For example, samples 18103 and 18107 on the one hand, and 117323, 117342 and 117365 on the other hand, could have been manufactured with two different clays (e.g. from different places), since each group shows clear differences on their elemental composition. Apart from this, other plausible hypothesis is the different burial location of the pigments, which could lead to different enrichments of leached metals of the soils. Nevertheless, to confirm this last hypothesis, a specific archaeological record of the recovery area would be needed.

3.4 Blue pigments

For the analysis of blue pigments the 532 nm excitation laser was used. The obtained spectra were the same for all analyzed samples, both, the ones from MANN and the ones from ARLP. Therefore, Raman results pointed out the same molecular composition of all blue studied samples. As shown in Fig. 6, these blue samples corresponded to Pompeian blue (most commonly known as Egyptian blue, Raman bands at 431, 479, 573 and 1086 cm^{-1}), which could be obtained by a natural way from cuprorivaite mineral (found in the Vesuvius lavas in a low content) or through chemical reactions described already by Vitruvius in first century BC [49]. This reaction consisted in mixing copper compounds with calcareous sand and a flux such as soda natron or plant ash. Due to both cuprorivaite low natural content in the Vesu-

vian area and the knowledge of preparing it through chemical reactions in the Roman period, it is expected that this blue pigments was not naturally obtained but it was manufactured chemically.

Fig. 6. Representative Raman spectrum of analyzed blue samples.

The elemental in situ analyses by means of XRF showed that Ca, Cu and Si were the major elements present in all the samples (see Fig. S7) confirming the previous obtained molecular results. Moreover, since the number of blue samples was high, it was decided to study the variability of the detected elements between samples by using the HH-ED-XRF results, following the same procedure done for the pink samples (see variability and correlation of the variables in Fig. S5 and S6 respectively). In this study elements such as P, S, Cl, Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Zn, Rb and Pb, showed high variability (see Fig. S5) depending on the considered sample. This high variability is also observed in the low correlation values showed in Fig. S6. The causes of these differences in the trace elemental composition of the final blue pigments must be related to the different source of the raw materials (copper compounds, limestone,

sand, etc.) taken for performing the chemical reaction to obtain the final pigment. However, Other possibility to find differences in trace elements could be the enrichment of metals present in soils, which can be leached during the burial, enriching the pigments with certain elements. As consequence of the different burial areas of the pigments, different enrichments of metals could have produced for each sample, obtaining nowadays different elemental compositions.

3.5 Yellow pigments

Microscopic observations under the 50x lens implemented in the video-microscope allowed to observe that these samples were composed mainly by yellow grains, but also by some blue and green grains in samples 117274 and 117359 respectively (see Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Microscopic observation (x50) of the composition of 117274 (left) and 117359 (right) yellow pigments.

Because of this heterogeneity, yellow, blue and green grains were analyzed separately by Raman spectroscopy. Unfortunately, due to the sampling interface of the HH-ED-XRF spectrometer (9 mm in diameter), the selective analysis of the different coloured grains was not possible to perform. Thus, XRF spectra of the bulk mixture were always recorded.

On the one hand, the Raman measurements of the yellow grains with the excitation laser of 785 nm produced the spectrum that is shown in Fig. 8 (on the left). The typical bands of goethite (α -FeOOH), the main component of the yellow ochre, can be observed at 246, 300, 387 and 533 cm^{-1} .

Fig. 8. Raman spectrum of yellow grains (left) and XRF spectrum of the mixture of yellow and blue grains (right) of pigment 117274.

On the other hand, both Raman spectra of the blue and green grains, that were present in sample 117274 and 117359 respectively, were acquired with the excitation laser of 532 nm because it offered better results. In this case, the obtained spectra came in agreement with those of Pompeian blue and malachite minerals used as pigment and previously identified

as the main coloured compound present in the analyzed blue and green samples. In this way different mixtures of pigments were identified, probably intentionally done to achieve colours with different shades that cannot be obtained by using pure pigments.

In situ XRF measurements of sample 117274 (Fig. 8 right) showed the composition of the mixture (yellow and blue grains). Fe was the major element because the presence of goethite in yellow grains, confirming in this way the results obtained by Raman technique.

Moreover, as shown in the XRF spectrum, other important elements were detected. In this case Pb was also detected in considerably high level as in the case of green samples, pointing out the possibility of the enrichment of Pb during the burial of the Pompeian pigments. Other XRF measurements confirmed the micro-Raman results since both blue and green grains provided the typical spectra of Pompeian blue (major elements Si, Ca and Cu) and malachite (major element Cu), with features very similar to the previously analyzed pure blue and green pigments.

3.6 White pigments

The analyzed white samples resulted to be dolomite ($\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2$). Moreover, as the obtained Raman spectrum showed, a little contribution of calcite (CaCO_3) was also observed (see Fig S8). Furthermore, as it was observed in the elemental analysis performed by means of HH-ED-XRF (see Fig. S9), Ca was identified as the major element. Unfortunately, the hand-held device is not able to detect lighter elements than Al, therefore, Mg was not detected, even being present in quite high level in the white sample as Raman results pointed out.

The molecular and elemental results obtained for the different pigments in this work are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Identified main molecular compounds in the studied samples.

Color	Identified main compound(s)	Identified Raman bands (cm^{-1})	Identified elements by XRF
Blue	Pompeian blue ($\text{CaCuSi}_4\text{O}_{10}$)	431 (s), 479 (w), 573 (w), 1086 (s)	Al, Si, P, S, Cl, K, Ca, Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Ni, Cu, Zn, Rb, Sr, Zr Pb
Pink	alizarin and purpurin	See ref. 48	Al, Si, P, K, Ca, Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Sr, Pb
Red	Red ochre (hematite)	224 (m), 243 (w), 291 (vs), 404 (vs), 608 (s)	Al, Si, P, S, K, Ca, Ti, V, Cr, Fe, Cu, Zn, As, Sr, Zr, Pb
	Cinnabar (HgS)	143 (s), 253 (vs), 284 (w), 344 (s)	Al, Si, P, S, K, Ca, Ti, Mn, Fe, Cu, As, Pb, Hg
Green	Malachite ($\text{Cu}_2\text{CO}_3(\text{OH})_2$)	154 (vs), 179 (vs), 220 (w), 269 (m), 352 (m), 433 (s), 534 (m), 719 (w), 1088 (w), 1367 (w) and 1493 (vs)	Al, Si, P, S, K, Ca, Ti, Mn, Fe, Cu, As, Pb
Yellow	Yellow ochre (goethite) Pompeian blue / malachite	246 (vw), 300 (w), 387 (m) and 533 (vw)	Al, Si, P, S, K, Ca, Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Pb
White	Dolomite $\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2$	176 (w), 299 (w), 723 (w), 1098 (m)	Al, Si, S, K, Ca, Ti, V, Mn, Fe, Cu, Pb, Sr

4. CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this research was to fully characterize in situ a wide variety of colours of unique Pompeian raw pigments, with high archaeological value recovered from the archaeological

burial of ancient Pompeii and nowadays stored in the Naples Archaeological National Museum and in the Applied Research Laboratory of Pompeii, following a non-invasive multi-analytical approach without consuming sample during the analysis. When the number of samples was high enough, a chemometric analysis was performed but never using the semi-quantitative concentration values of elements given by the instrument; instead of that, the net counts of the detected elements, normalized against Compton line of each measurement, were used.

The present work shows the importance that portable non-invasive techniques have nowadays in the cultural heritage field analysis. In this sense, a complete characterization of the molecular compounds present in the studied samples or materials was achieved in situ, avoiding problems regarding to sampling procedures and losses or contaminations of these unique archaeological records. The results regarding the composition of these pigments were successfully obtained. In this sense, red and yellow ochres, mercury sulphide, malachite, Pompeian blue, madder lake and dolomite were successfully identified in the analyzed pigments. Apart from that, mixtures of different colored pigments were identified, probably with the intention of the artists of generating new color hues impossible to achieve without this procedure.

Thanks to the performed statistical study and Principal Component Analysis, differences in the elemental composition were identified, probably due to two different possible causes. On the one hand, the different source of the raw mineral (in the case of Pompeian blue) or the clay (in the case of pink lake pigments), which have different elemental composition at

minor/trace level. On the other hand, the different area in which the pigments have been buried for thousands of years, which could led to different enrichments of metal presents in soils due to leaching processes, changing in this way the original elemental composition. Finally, it must be remarked the unexpected high presence of lead in some pigments. Previous works [10] demonstrated that Pompeian pink lake pigments, recovered from the archaeological burial, show a high concentration of lead due to an enrichment on this metal, which can come from the leaching process of the lead pipe system used in the ancient city of Pompeii. Therefore, in this work we present additional evidences that confirm the inclusion of this metal in additional buried raw pigments from this ancient Roman city.

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REFERENCES

- [1] P. Foss, J. J. Dobbins, *The world of Pompeii*. Routledge, London, 2009.
- [2] G. Luongo, A. Perrotta, C. Scarpati, E. De Carolis, G. Patricelli, A. Ciarallo, Impact of the AD 79 explosive eruption on Pompeii, II. Causes of death of the inhabitants inferred by stratigraphic analysis and areal distribution of the human casualties, *J. Volcanol. Geoth. Res.* 126 (2003) 169-200.
- [3] M. Maguregui, U. Knuutinen, J. Trebolazabala, H. Morillas, K. Castro, I. Martínez-Arkarazo, J.M. Madariaga, Use of in situ and confocal Raman spectroscopy to study the nature and distribution of carotenoids in brown patinas from a deteriorated wall painting in Marcus Lucretius House (Pompeii), *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 402 (2012) 1529-1539.
- [4] M. Maguregui, U. Knuutinen, I. Martínez-Arkarazo, A. Giakoumaki, K. Castro, J.M. Madariaga, Field Raman analysis to diagnose the conservation state of excavated walls and wall paintings in the archaeological site of Pompeii (Italy), *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 43 (2012) 1747-1753.
- [5] J.M. Madariaga, M. Maguregui, K. Castro, U. Knuutinen, I. Martínez-Arkarazo, Portable Raman, DRIFTS, and XRF Analysis to Diagnose the Conservation State of Two Wall Painting Panels from Pompeii Deposited in the Naples National Archaeological Museum (Italy), *Appl. Spectrosc.* 70 (2016) 137-146.

- [6] I. Marcaida, M. Maguregui, S. Fdez-Ortiz de Vallejuelo, H. Morillas, N. Prieto-Taboada, M. Veneranda, K. Castro, J.M. Madariaga, In situ X-ray fluorescence-based method to differentiate among red ochre pigments and yellow ochre pigments thermally transformed to red pigments of wall paintings from Pompeii, *Anal. Bional. Chem.* 409 (2017) 3853-3860.
- [7] D. Hradil, T. Grygar, J. Hradilová, P. Bezdička, Clay and iron oxide pigments in the history of painting, *Appl. Clay Sci.* 22 (2003) 223-236.
- [8] F. Froment, A. Tournié, P. Colomban, Raman identification of natural red to yellow pigments: ochre and iron-containing ores, *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 39 (2008) 560-568.
- [9] B. Gilbert, S. Denoel, G. Weber, D. Allart, Analysis of green copper pigments in illuminated manuscripts by micro-Raman spectroscopy, *Analyst*, 128 (2003) 1213-1217.
- [10] I. Marcaida, M. Maguregui, H. Morillas, C. García-Florentino, U. Knuutinen, J.A. Carrero, S. Fdez-Ortiz de Vallejuelo, A. Pitarch, K. Castro, J.M. Madariaga, Multi-spectroscopic and isotopic ratio analysis to characterize the inorganic binder used on Pompeian pink and purple lake pigments, *Anal. Chem.* 88 (2016) 6395-6402.
- [11] M.L. Vázquez De Agredos Pascual, M.T. Domenech, A. Domenech, The colour palette in the architecture of la blanca (Petén, Guatemala). Comparison between that of the Mayan lowlands and that used in other civilizations of the ancient world, *Arché.* 2 (2007) 125-130.
- [12] E. Hovers, S. Ilani, B. Vandermeersch, O. Bar-Yosef, B. Vandermeersch, An early case of color symbolism: Ochre use by modern humans in Qafzeh Cave 1, *Curr. Anthropol.* 44 (2003) 491-522.

- [13] F. Ospitali, D.C. Smith, M. Lorblanchet, Preliminary investigations by Raman microscopy of prehistoric pigments in the wall-painted cave at Roucadour, Quercy, France, *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 37 (2006) 1063-1071.
- [14] C.J. Cooksey, Tyrian purple: 6, 6'-dibromoindigo and related compounds, *Molecules.* 6 (2001) 736-769.
- [15] M. Maguregui, U. Knuutinen, I. Martínez-Arkarazo, K. Castro, J.M. Madariaga, Thermodynamic and spectroscopic speciation to explain the blackening process of hematite formed by atmospheric SO₂ impact: The Case of Marcus Lucretius House (Pompeii), *Anal. Chem.* 83, (2011) 3319-3326.
- [16] J.M. Madariaga, M. Maguregui, S. Fdez-Ortiz de Vallejuelo, U. Knuutinen, K. Castro, I. Martinez-Arkarazo, A. Giakoumaki, A. Pitarch, In situ analysis with portable Raman and ED-XRF spectrometers for the diagnosis of the formation of efflorescence on walls and wall paintings of the Insula IX 3 (Pompeii, Italy), *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 45 (2014) 1059-1067.
- [17] M. Maguregui, K. Castro, H. Morillas, J. Trebolazabala, U. Knuutinen, R. Wiesinger, M. Schreiner, J.M. Madariaga, Multianalytical approach to explain the darkening process of hematite pigment in paintings from ancient Pompeii after accelerated weathering experiments, *Anal. Methods-UK* , 6 (2014) 372-378.
- [18] M. Radepont, Y. Coquinot, K. Janssens, J.J. Ezrati, W. de Nolf, M.Cotte, Thermodynamic and experimental study of the degradation of the red pigment mercury sulfide, *J. Anal. Atom. Spectrom.* 30 (2015) 599-612.

- [19] S. Augusti, *I colori pompeiani*, 1967. De Luca; Roma
- [20] H. Davy, Some experiments and observations on the colours used in painting by the ancients. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond.* 1815;105:97–124.
- [21] M. Clarke, P. Frederickx, M.P. Colombini, A. Andreotti, J. Wouters, M. van Bommel, N. Eastaugh, V. Walsh, T. Chaplin, R. Siddall, “Pompei purpurissim pigment problems”, *Proceedings of Art’05–8th international conference on “Non Destructive Investigations and Microanalysis for the Diagnostics and Conservation of the Cultural and Environmental Heritage”*, Lecce, Italy, AIPnD, Brescia (2005).
- [22] I. Aliatis, D. Bersani, E. Campani, A. Casoli, P. P. Lottici, S. Mantovan, I. G. Marino, Pigments used in Roman wall paintings in the Vesuvian area, *J. Raman Spectrosc*, 41, (2010) 1537-1542.
- [23] H. Morillas, M. Maguregui, I. Marcaida, J. Trebolazabala, I. Salcedo, J.M. Madariaga, Characterization of the main colonizer and biogenic pigments present in the red biofilm from La Galea Fortress sandstone by means of microscopic observations and Raman imaging, *Microchem. J.* 121 (2015) 48-55.
- [24] A. Gianoncelli, J. Castaing, L. Ortega, E. Dooryhee, J. Salomon, P. Walter, J.L. Hodeau, P. Bordet, A portable instrument for in situ determination of the chemical and phase compositions of cultural heritage objects, *X-Ray Spectrom.* 37 (2008) 418-423.

- [25] H. Morillas, I. Marcaida, M. Maguregui, J.A. Carrero, J.M. Madariaga, The influence of rainwater composition on the conservation state of cementitious building materials, *Sci. Total Environ.* 542 (2016) 716-727.
- [26] G. Vittiglio, S. Bichlmeier, P. Klinger, J. Heckel, W. Fuzhong, L. Vincze,... & D. Jembrih-Simbürger, A compact μ -XRF spectrometer for (in situ) analyses of cultural heritage and forensic materials, *Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res. Sect. B*, 213 (2004) 693-698.
- [27] H. Morillas, J. García-Galan, M. Maguregui, C. García-Florentino, I. Marcaida, J.A. Carrero, J.M. Madariaga, In-situ multianalytical methodology to evaluate the conservation state of the entrance arch of La Galea Fortress (Getxo, north of Spain), *Microchem. J.* 128 (2016) 288-296.
- [28] C. Miliani, F. Rosi, B.G. Brunetti, A. Sgamellotti, In situ noninvasive study of artworks: the MOLAB multitechnique approach, *Accounts Chem. Res.* 43 (2010) 728-738.
- [29] H. Morillas, J. García-Galan, M. Maguregui, I. Marcaida, C. García-Florentino, J.A. Carrero, J.M. Madariaga, Assessment of marine and urban-industrial environments influence on built heritage sandstone using X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy and complementary techniques, *Spectrochim. Acta B*. 123 (2016) 76-88.
- [30] C. García-Florentino, M. Maguregui, H. Morillas, I. Marcaida, J.M. Madariaga, A fast in situ non-invasive approach to classify mortars from a construction of high historical value, *Microchem. J.* 133 (2017) 104-113.
- [31] M. Veneranda, N. Prieto-Taboada, S. Fdez- Ortiz de Vallejuelo, M. Maguregui, H. Morillas, I. Marcaida, K. Castro, J.M. Madariaga, M. Osanna, Biodeterioration of Pompeian mural

paintings: fungal colonization favoured by the presence of volcanic material residues. *Environ. Sci. Poll. Res.* (2017), DOI: 10.1007/s11356-017-9570-8

[32] A. Derbyshire, R. Withnall, Pigment analysis of portrait miniatures using Raman microscopy, *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 30 (1999) 185-188.

[33] A. Rosalie David, H.G.M. Edwards, D.W. Farwell, D.L.A. De Faria, Raman spectroscopic analysis of ancient Egyptian pigments, *Archaeometry*, 43 (2001) 461-473.

[34] M. Sawczak, A. Kamińska, G. Rabczuk, M. Ferretti, R. Jendrzewski, G. Śliwiński, Complementary use of the Raman and XRF techniques for non-destructive analysis of historical paint layers, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 255 (2009) 5542-5545.

[35] Appolonia, L., Vaudan, D., Chatel, V., Aceto, M., & Mirti, P. (2009). Combined use of FORS, XRF and Raman spectroscopy in the study of mural paintings in the Aosta Valley (Italy). *Analytical and bioanalytical chemistry*, 395(7), 2005-2013.

[36] À. Pitarch, J. F. Ruiz, S. Fernandez-Ortiz de Vallejuelo, A. Hernanz, M. Maguregui, J.M. Madariaga, In situ characterization by Raman and X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy of post-Paleolithic blackish pictographs exposed to the open air in Los Chaparros shelter (Albalate del Arzobispo, Teruel, Spain), *Anal. Methods-UK*, 6 (2014) 6641-6650.

[37] A. Ben Younès-Krandel, Boite à fard. In (M. H. Fantar, Ed.) "Tunisie. Terre de rencontres et de civilisation". Tunis: Agence Nationale du Patrimoine (1992).

[38] J. Carington-Smith, A roman chamber tomb on the southeast slopes of Monasteriki Kephala, Knossos, *British School of Athens*, 77 (1982) 272-293.

- [39] T. Karmous, N. Ayed, M.H. Fantar, J. Wouters, *Dyes in History and Archaeology*, 14 (1996) 3–8.
- [40] J. Pérez-Arantegui, J.A. Paz-Peralta, E Ortiz-Palomar, Analysis of the Products Contained in Two Roman Glass Unguentaria from the Colony of Celsa (Spain), *J. Archaeol. Sci.* 23 (1996) 649–655.
- [41] P. Walter, E Van Elslande, Les analyses chimiques des fards. In "Le Bain et le Miroir". Gallimard, Paris. (2009) 126–141
- [42] M. Maguregui, N. Prieto-Taboada, J. Trebolazabala, N. Goienaga, N. Arrieta, J. Aramendia, L. Gomez-Nubla, A. Sarmiento, M. Olivares, J.A. Carrero, I. Martinez-Arkarazo, K. Castro, G. Arana, M.A. Olazabal, L.A. Fernandez, J.M. Madariaga, 2010. CHEMCH 1st International Congress Chemistry for Cultural Heritage, Ravenna, 30th June–3rd July.
- [43] R.T. Downs, M. Hall-Wallace, 2002. A database of crystal structures published in the *American mineralogist* and the *Canadian mineralogist* and its use as a resource in the classroom. 18th General Meeting of the International Mineralogical Association, p. 128.
- [44] C. García-Florentino, M. Maguregui, H. Morillas, I. Marcaida, J. M. Madariaga, A fast in situ non-invasive approach to classify mortars from a construction of high historical value, *Microchem. J.* 133 (2017) 104-113.
- [45] C. D. Harris, *Cinnabar: The Symbolic, Seductive, Sublethal Shade of Pompeii*, 2015 (Doctoral dissertation).

- [46] R. Santacroce, R. Cioni, P. Marianelli, A. Sbrana, R. Sulpizio, G. Zanchetta, D.J. Donahue, J.L. Joron, Age and whole rock–glass compositions of proximal pyroclastics from the major explosive eruptions of Somma-Vesuvius: A review as a tool for distal tephrostratigraphy, *J. Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.*, 177 (2008) 1-18.
- [47] I. Aliatis, D. Bersani, E. Campani, A. Casoli, P. P. Lottici, S. Mantovan,... F. Ospitali, Green pigments of the Pompeian artists' palette. *Spectrochim. Acta A*, 73 (2009) 532-538.
- [48] I. Marcaida, M. Maguregui, H. Morillas, C. García-Florentino, V. Pintus, T. Aguayo, M. Campos-Vallette, J.M. Madariaga, Optimization of sample treatment for the identification of anthraquinone dyes by surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 409 (2017) 2221-2228.
- [49] G.A. Mazzocchin, D. Rudello, C. Bragato, F. Agnoli, A short note on Egyptian blue, *J. Cult. Her.* 5 (2004) 129-133.

FIGURE CAPTIONS

Fig. 1. Some of the studied pigments (in the left part) in their original bowls and in a shell: a) 117333 blue b) 11699 green c) 117366 yellow and d) 64628 red; In the right part, measuring the pigments directly by Raman spectroscopy in the ARLP.

Fig. 2. Red pigment 64628. Raman and HH-ED-XRF in situ acquired spectra.

Fig. 3. Raman spectra of red pigment 112251.

Fig. 4. Raman spectrum of green pigment samples 41505 (red) and 11699 (blue).

Fig. 5. Principal Component Analysis of the analyzed pink samples (bi-plot representation).

Fig. 6. Representative Raman spectrum of analyzed blue samples.

Fig. 7. Microscopic observation (x50) of the composition of 117274 (left) and 117359 (right) yellow pigments.

Fig. 8. Raman spectrum of yellow grains (left) and XRF spectrum of the mixture of yellow and blue grains (right) of pigment 117274.

HIGHLIGHTS

A UNIQUE COLLECTION OF POMPEIAN PIGMENTS WITH HIGH ARCHAEOLOGICAL WAS ANALYZED IN-SITU BY NON INVASIVE TECHNIQUES.

THE COMPOUNDS RESPONSIBLE TO GIVE THE COLOR AND THE MANUFACTURING WAY WERE IDENTIFIED.

DIFFERENCES IN THE ELEMENTAL COMPOSITION WERE DETECTED, PROBABLY BECAUSE DIFFERENT SOURCE MATERIALS OR DIFFERENT ENRICHMENTS DURING THE BURIAL.

AN UNEXPECTED HIGH CONTENT IN Pb WAS OBSERVED IN SOME CASES, PROBABLY DUE TO ENRICHMENTS COMING FROM VARIOUS LIXIVIATIONS.

ACCEPTED MANUSCRIPT